

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

No6
MAXSUS SON

BAKALAVR TALABALARINIG MAQOLALARI TO'PLAMI

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2025

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'z.Respub. Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhmatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi

Elektron nashr. 98 sahifa.

E'lon qilishga 2025-yil mayda ruxsat etildi.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

- Salimov Okil Umrzokovich**, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjavevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of Department, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of DCEC, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhmatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilkhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Khusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Rakhimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridakhon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 28-fevraldagi 333/5-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

Strategies for achieving sustainable growth through green economy transition.....	14
Umida Kakhramonova Gayratovna, Tillayev Khurshidjon Sulaymon oglu	
Current state and development prospects of tourism: comparative analysis and Uzbekistan's experience.....	20
Risolatbonu Shakhzodova, Laziza Khalilova, Nabijonov Biloliddin, Aziza Usmanova	
Инновационные подходы к повышению эффективности корпоративного управления.....	26
Тлеумуратова Мадинабону Дилмурат кизи, Уринов Бабур Насиллоевич	
Startup проекты и их реализация	30
Ёдгорова Мухайе Шухратовна, Иминова Наргиза Акрамовна	
Methodology of Teaching English: Traditional and Modern Approaches	34
Ravshanova Ziyoda Qahramon Qizi, Xoliqova Dilafruz Shuhratovna	
Государственный кредит и государственный долг.....	37
Срождиддинова З.Х., Тухтасинова Д.Н.	
Сравнительный анализ реформ государственных финансов в Китае и Грузии: уроки для Узбекистана	42
Срождиддинова Зарина Хайриддиновна, Шарифзода Мубина Дилмуроджон кизи	
Korxonalarda asosiy vositalar hisobini yuritishni takomillashtirish	49
Shakarov Shahzod Sobir o'g'li, Po'latov Xudoyberdi Uktamovich, Esanov Oybek Madatovich	
Sustainable consumption and production: economic challenges and solutions.....	55
Abdullayev Abdug'ofur, Abdubaxromov Abduazim, Eshniyozov Ozodbek, Azizbek Abdullayev	
Traffic congestion in Uzbekistan: causes and strategic solutions	60
Abdulloh Qodirov, Imron Egamberdiyev, Isomiddin Ravshanov, Munisa Bekmirzayeva	
The relationship between corruption and economic growth.....	64
Jurayev Jo'rabek, Abdullayeva Aziza, Mamatova Sarvinoz, Maha Ibrahim	
Crisis management in the tourism industry	74
Ikromova Munisa, Bahodirova Mohigul, Xalimova Dilbar, Abdullajonova Muslimabonu	
Impact of the touristic indicators on the poverty rate.....	80
Abdumanova Maftuna, Azizova Ruhshona, Shavkatova Mubiynabonu, Durdona Bahodirova	
Bringing sustainability: the role of the green economy in enhancing resource efficiency	91
Salokhiddinova Farangiz, Mardonov MuhammadYusuf, Shovkiyeva Munisa, Ahmadova Xurshida	

BRINGING SUSTAINABILITY: THE ROLE OF THE GREEN ECONOMY IN ENHANCING RESOURCE EFFICIENCY

Salokhiddinova Farangiz

Foundation student of the International Double Degree Faculty of TSUE with IMC UAS Krems
salokhiddinovafarangiz@gmail.com
ORCID: 0009-0008-9060-353X

Mardonov MuhammadYusuf

Foundation student of the International Double Degree Faculty of TSUE with IMC UAS Krems
mardonovmuhammadyusuf6@gmail.com
ORCID: 0009-0001-2318-4813

Ahmadova Xurshida

Foundation student of the International Double Degree Faculty of TSUE with IMC UAS Krems
xurshidaahmedova06@gmail.com
ORCID: 0009-0006-6195-1602

Shovkiyeva Munisa

assistant of IMC Krems Transnational Department,
Tashkent State University of Economics
munisashovqiyeva2000@gmail.com
ORCID: 0009-0008-7187-2443
Scientific supervisor

Abstract: This paper explores the effectiveness of resource efficiency and energy intensity strategies in selected countries using a mixed-methods approach. It analyzes how nations such as Sweden and Canada have successfully aligned environmental and economic objectives, while countries like China face complex challenges in transitioning to a green economy. The study highlights the role of institutional capacity, clean energy adoption, and sustainable development policies in reducing material and energy intensity. Results show that higher-income countries demonstrate better performance in energy efficiency, whereas developing countries still face rising material demand. The findings suggest that national policy coherence and investment in green infrastructure are critical to advancing the global green economy.

Key words: resource efficiency, energy intensity, green economy, Sweden, Canada, China, renewable energy, environmental policy, sustainable development.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada resurslardan samarali foydalanish va energiya intensivligini kamaytirish bo'yicha siyosatlarining samaradorligi tahlil qilinadi. Aralash metodlar asosida olib borilgan tadqiqotda Shvetsiya va Kanada singari mamlakatlar ekologik va iqtisodiy maqsadlarni muvofiqlashtirishga erishgani, Xitoy esa yashil iqtisodiyotga o'tishda murakkab muammolarga duch kelayotgani ko'rsatiladi. Tadqiqot natijalari resurs samaradorligini oshirishda institutsional salohiyat, qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalaridan foydalanish va barqaror taraqqiyot siyosatining muhimligini ta'kidlaydi. Yuqori daromadli mamlakatlarda energiya samaradorligi yuqori bo'lsa-da, rivojlanayotgan davlatlarda resurs iste'moli oshishda davom etmoqda. Xulosa qilib aytganda, yashil iqtisodiyotga o'tishda siyosiy uyg'unlik va yashil infratuzilmaga sarmoya kiritish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: resurs samaradorligi, energiya intensivligi, yashil iqtisodiyot, Shvetsiya, Kanada, Xitoy, qayta tiklanuvchi energiya, ekologik siyosat, barqaror rivojlanish.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается эффективность стратегий повышения ресурсоэффективности и снижения энергоёмкости в отдельных странах с применением смешанных методов исследования. Анализ показывает, что Швеция и Канада успешно совмещают экологические и экономические цели, в то время как Китай сталкивается со сложностями в переходе к зелёной экономике. Исследование подчёркивает значимость институционального потенциала, внедрения возобновляемых источников энергии и устойчивой государственной политики. Результаты показывают, что страны с высоким доходом добились значительного прогресса в области энергоэффективности, в то время как в развивающихся странах сохраняется рост потребления материалов. Вывод заключается в том, что согласованная государственная политика и инвестиции в зелёную инфраструктуру являются ключевыми факторами для продвижения глобальной зелёной экономики.

Ключевые слова: ресурсоэффективность, энергоёмкость, зелёная экономика, Швеция, Канада, Китай, возобновляемая энергия, экологическая политика, устойчивое развитие.

INTRODUCTION

Low-carbon, resource-efficient, and socially balanced growth are the main goals of the green economy [1]. The purpose of investments and policies in a green economy is to increase resource and energy efficiency while simultaneously promoting social and economic advancement. Lower material use—or higher resource efficiency helps reduce environmental issues and sustains long-term economic growth [2]. Resource efficiency is critical not only for environmental sustainability but also for economic resilience, as inefficient resource use causes severe damage to ecosystems and society (OECD, 2017).

For instance, global material flows could nearly double from approximately 41 billion tonnes in 2010 to about 89 billion tonnes by 2050 due to urbanization and increased consumption levels [3]. This is a serious concern given the sharp rise in global material use over the past few decades. Such a trend has led to considerable environmental impacts, including biodiversity loss, increased greenhouse gas emissions, and ecosystem degradation. As a result, decoupling economic growth from material and energy consumption has become a central objective in the agenda of sustainable development [UNEP and the OECD].

One notable example is the European Union, where resource productivity (GDP per unit of material used) increased by 39% between 2000 and 2017 [4], indicating some success in decoupling economic activity from material consumption. Nevertheless, rising demands for resources remain a pressing challenge, especially in middle- and low-income countries due to ongoing infrastructure development, industrial growth, and population increase [OECD, 2020]. Consequently, the operationalization of green economy principles often varies depending on a country's development priorities, institutional capacity, and governance structures.

We argue that many previous studies either focus on single-country cases or present overly broad global overviews. Furthermore, most of them emphasize carbon emission reduction or isolated environmental metrics to assess resource efficiency. Therefore, we contend that it is crucial to conduct comparative research involving diverse economic systems and policy frameworks across regions such as Europe, North America, and Asia.

Our study integrates material use, energy intensity, and economic productivity to provide a more multidimensional assessment of sustainability [UNEP and the OECD]. Quantitatively, we examine key indicators such as energy intensity (energy use per unit of GDP), material productivity (GDP per unit of material consumption), and the share of renewable energy in national energy mixes. Qualitatively, we evaluate national policy frameworks reflecting green economy principles and assess their effectiveness in achieving resource-efficient outcomes.

Ultimately, this study seeks to contribute to a better understanding of how countries at various stages of development can harmonize environmental sustainability with economic performance. We hypothesize that nations with well-established green economy strategies will demonstrate higher levels of resource efficiency compared to those with less comprehensive policy frameworks.

REVIEW OF RELEVANT LITERATURE

The green economy model connects sustainable resource use with economic growth. By definition, the green economy greatly reduces environmental risks and ecological scarcity while increasing social equity and human well-being [5]. Most modern green growth strategies generally focus on resource productivity and efficient use of natural inputs [Februari 2025, Loso Judijanto]. Current strategies prioritize reducing carbon emissions, increasing resource efficiency, and promoting circular economy concepts, according to Judijanto's analysis of green economy policies. Furthermore, the idea of a "green economy" refers to the reduction in the overuse of natural resources even as output and employment continue to grow. Green economy projects such as using renewable energy, promoting green public procurement, and enhancing recycling efforts are essentially geared toward increasing the rate of material reuse and improving resource consumption patterns, in line with SDG 12 on sustainable consumption.

At the international level, policy analyses confirm that enhancing resource efficiency is a central goal of green growth. The OECD [2020] highlights that many countries have developed strategies aimed at achieving a more circular and resource-efficient economy, such as those under the Sustainable Development Goals and the G7 Resource Efficiency Action Plans. However, structural and technological changes alone will not suffice to curb the rising global material consumption unless supplemented by additional policy instruments [OECD, 2019]. This indicates that the decoupling of resource use from economic growth must remain a core focus of green economy frameworks. OECD projections suggest that, without serious interventions, material usage in OECD countries could grow by up to 65% by 2060 [6]. Therefore, the organization emphasizes that well-planned green economic policies that integrate incentives, regulatory mechanisms, and innovation support tend to be more effective, whereas fragmented approaches are typically insufficient to boost resource productivity.

Case studies help illustrate these dynamics. Sweden, widely recognized as a leader in green growth, has long implemented policies such as carbon pricing, renewable energy promotion, and circular economy initiatives. According to the OECD [2025] environmental review, "Sweden successfully decoupled major environmental pressures from economic growth" over the past decade [7]. This decoupling is evident in Sweden's high levels of resource productivity, with greenhouse gas and energy intensities per GDP among the lowest in the European Union [8]. Sweden's long-term climate strategy prioritizes digitalization and smart systems to increase resource efficiency, particularly in energy and waste management. In practice, its green growth policy mix including a comprehensive carbon tax since 1991 and extensive R&D in cleantech—has delivered measurable improvements in material and energy efficiency, in line with international green economy benchmarks.

Canada presents a more mixed scenario. Despite being a resource-rich and historically energy-intensive economy, Canada has made progress in implementing green policies. According to the OECD [2017] environmental review, the country has achieved some decoupling of economic growth from air pollution, energy use, and greenhouse gas emissions. Nevertheless, Canada continues to rank among the most resource-intensive economies globally since 2000 [9]. Empirical studies indicate that green economy strategies can significantly mitigate environmental impacts. For instance, a 2023 study found that improved resource efficiency especially through circular economy initiatives helps reduce ecological harm in Canada [10]. Moreover, Canadian policy documents acknowledge that without stronger efficiency measures, the country's already high per capita resource use (one of the highest in the G8) will hinder its transition to a low-carbon economy [9].

Similarly, China is increasingly integrating resource-efficiency goals into its broader green growth agenda. Recent Five-Year Plans include targets for building an "ecological civilization," promoting circular economy principles, reducing energy intensity, and applying resource taxation. Scholars report that China's policy tools such as mandatory recycling and industrial modernization are beginning to slow the growth of material and energy use. Nonetheless, due to the scale of its economy, China's total material consumption remains very

high. Studies (e.g., Takalo et al., 2021) emphasize the need for innovation in green technologies and financing mechanisms to further accelerate efficiency improvements.

DATA AND METHODOLOGY

In our study, we applied a mixed-methods framework combining data analysis and policy review. Quantitatively, we gathered published indicators of resource efficiency and productivity from sources such as Eurostat/EEA, IEA, and the World Bank database (e.g., GDP per unit of domestic material consumption, energy use per GDP, and renewable energy share). Qualitatively, we examined strategic policy documents and national strategies, such as Sweden's Climate Policy Framework as assessed by OECD [2025] [11], Canada's Pan-Canadian Framework on Clean Growth and Climate Change [12], and China's 14th Five-Year Plan (2021–2025) [13]. These policies encompass measures such as carbon pricing, efficiency standards, and technology investments that influence resource-use outcomes.

By triangulating trends in quantitative data with insights from policy analyses, we aim to highlight general global trends and illustrative regional experiences.

Resource efficiency is inherently the result of both technical and policy-driven processes, shaped by strategic governance frameworks, investments, and institutional capacities. Therefore, analyzing this topic from a single methodological perspective would be insufficient.

The metrics we utilize from databases such as Eurostat/EEA, IEA, and the World Bank provide comparative insight into how different economies are performing relative to one another and in relation to global sustainability benchmarks.

However, quantitative metrics alone cannot fully capture the institutional and policy mechanisms driving these trends. Hence, we supplement the analysis with a review of policy documents that serve as authoritative articulations of governmental intent and action within the green economy transition.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Resource efficiency metrics show mixed progress. Energy intensity (energy use per GDP) has generally declined, but unevenly. For example, recent analyses find a modest 1% drop in global energy intensity in 2023 far below the historical average of 1.8% per year recorded in the 2010s [14]. Within the OECD, however, improvements were much stronger: 2023 saw a 3.1% fall in energy intensity, including a 4.7% drop in the EU and more than 2% declines in the US and Canada [14].

By contrast, many nonOECD regions saw little change or even an increase. Notably, China's energy intensity rose by approximately 1.3% in 2023 [14]. Globally, material use remains high and is projected to grow further. Developed countries still consume significantly more per capita than low-income countries, and the fastest growth in material demand is occurring in Asia and Africa.

Figure 1: Share of electricity production from renewables (1985–2024) by country income group (source: Our World in Data, CC BY).

Figure 1 illustrates that high- and upper-middle-income countries reached approximately 25–30% renewable share of electricity by the mid-2020s (including hydro, wind, solar, etc.), with the world average share approaching ~28%. Low-income countries appear much higher (reflecting hydropower dependence), but these are small economies. The continuing rise in renewable shares indicates substantial efficiency gains. For example, many European countries and Canada have extensive hydro and wind installations, while China is currently the leader in solar and wind installations.

Case – Sweden (Europe): Sweden is an example of an ambitious green economy approach. Its climate framework and the recent OECD review explicitly call for making “energy and resource efficiency a fundamental component” of climate transition policies [11]. This aligns with strong performance: Sweden’s energy intensity fell by ~38% from 2005 to 2023, roughly matching EU trends [15]. The country has world-class district heating and combined heat-and-power systems which reuse waste heat [15]. Sweden is also a leading nation in recycling and circular policies; among its national goals are high municipal recycling rates and a halving of material intensity between 2005 and 2030.

Case – Canada (North America): Canada’s clean growth strategy connects economic and environmental goals in a similar way. Key measures include carbon pricing, support for clean technology, and efficiency standards. Canada already operates a mostly non-emitting grid: approximately 80% of its electricity comes from hydro, nuclear, wind, and solar sources, and the government has committed to reaching 90% non-emitting power by 2030 [16]. Energy intensity has also fallen: OECD data indicate that North America saw a decline in energy intensity of over 2% in 2023 [14].

Case – China (Asia): China’s 14th Five-Year Plan (2021–2025) prioritizes “green development” and resource efficiency. Combining heavy industries into current industrial parks (for improved energy management), modifying the steel and building sectors, and implementing large-scale renewable energy projects are key measures included [13]. Indeed, China is driving global renewable expansion: an IEA forecast estimates that China will supply ~40% of all new renewable capacity between 2019 and 2024 [17]. However, China also faces constraints its economy still relies heavily on coal (China uses approximately 25% of the world’s coal for power). In 2023, China’s energy intensity unexpectedly increased (+1.3%) [14†], suggesting that the pace of economic growth and existing infrastructure can offset potential efficiency gains.

Development of resource productivity in comparison with GDP and DMC, EU, 2000-2023
(2000 = 100)

Note: GDP in chain-linked volumes, reference year 2015. Y-axis does not start at 0
Source: Eurostat (online data code: nama_10_gdp; env_ac_mfa; env_ac_rp)

eurostat

Figure 2: Resource productivity in comparison with GDP and DMC, EU, 2000-2023

Source: Eurostat [18] [19] [20].

Figure 2 illustrates that resource productivity is measured as gross domestic product (GDP) over domestic material consumption (DMC). The latter measures the total amount of materials directly consumed in an economy by businesses for economic production and by households. The former is a basic measure for the overall size of a country’s economy. It is obvious from the graph that DMC has been keeping up with the development of resource productivity, while GDP has shown a downward trend since 2000.

Energy intensity measured in terms of primary energy and GDP

Figure 3: Energy intensity levels measured in terms of primary energy and GDP

Source: This indicator is derived from energy data sourced on a joint dataset built by the International

Energy Agency (<https://www.iea.org/data-and-statistics/>) and the United Nations Statistics Division (<https://unstats.un.org/unsd/energystats/>).

Figure 3, sourced from the IEA, illustrates energy intensity in terms of primary energy consumption relative to GDP. Since 2000, energy intensity in both Canada and Sweden has declined steadily over the years, while China has experienced an uptick. Notably, only Canada's energy intensity exceeded the world average (4.6 MJ per 2017 USD PPP), reaching 6.6 MJ per 2017 USD PPP in 2021. In contrast, Sweden and China recorded 3.5 MJ and 0.8 MJ per 2017 USD PPP, respectively.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Using a mixed-methods approach, we found that countries with well-developed policy-making structures—such as Sweden and Canada have achieved significant improvements in energy and material efficiency, effectively aligning environmental goals with economic growth. China, on the other hand, presents a dynamic yet complex case: despite leading global efforts in renewable energy expansion, its continued reliance on coal and rapid industrialization hinder substantial efficiency gains.

Although global energy intensity is generally declining, much of this progress is concentrated in higher-income economies. In contrast, emerging economies continue to experience rising material consumption, which underscores the necessity for deeper structural reforms and long-term policy commitments.

These findings provide strong support for the hypothesis that robust institutional frameworks, targeted investments, and comprehensive sustainability strategies are critical to enhancing resource efficiency.

To conclude, the green economy should be viewed not as a one-size-fits-all solution, but rather as a flexible policy framework whose success depends on a nation's capacity for coherent planning, governance, and adaptation to local economic and environmental realities.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE

1. United Nations Environment Programme. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://www.unep.org/>
2. European Union. (n.d.). Retrieved from https://european-union.europa.eu/index_en
3. World Economic Forum. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://www.weforum.org/>
4. European Environment Agency. (2018). Resource efficiency and low-carbon economy. Retrieved from <https://www.eea.europa.eu/airs/2018/resource-efficiency-and-low-carbon-economy/resource-efficiency>
5. Adisam Publisher. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://adisampublisher.org/>
6. OECD. (n.d.). Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. Retrieved from <https://www.oecd.org/>
7. OECD. (2025). Environmental Performance Reviews: Sweden 2025. Retrieved from https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/2025/03/oecd-environmental-performance-reviews-sweden-2025_409c4061.html

8. OECD. (2025). Innovation Scoreboard & Environmental Indicators. Retrieved from https://www.oecd.org/content/dam/oecd/en/publications/reports/2025/03/oecd-environmental-performance-reviews-sweden-2025_409c4061/91dcc109-en.pdf
9. OECD. (2017). Environmental Performance Reviews: Canada 2017. Retrieved from https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/2017/12/oecd-environmental-performance-reviews-canada-2017_g1g7f690.html
10. Frontiers in Environmental Science. (2023). Impact of Circular Economy on Resource Efficiency in Canada. Retrieved from <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/environmental-science/articles/10.3389/fenvs.2023.1276632/full>
11. OECD. (2025). Sweden Climate Policy Framework Review. Retrieved from https://www.oecd.org/content/dam/oecd/en/publications/reports/2025/03/oecd-environmental-performance-reviews-sweden-2025_409c4061/91dcc109-en.pdf
12. Government of Canada. (n.d.). Pan-Canadian Framework on Clean Growth and Climate Change. Retrieved from <https://www.canada.ca/en/services/environment/weather/climatechange/pan-canadian-framework.html>
13. Government of China. (2022). China's 14th Five-Year Plan (2021–2025). Retrieved from https://english.www.gov.cn/policies/latestreleases/202201/24/content_WS61ee88b6c6d09c94e48a4301.html
14. Enerdata. (2023). Global Energy Intensity Trends. Retrieved from <https://yearbook.enerdata.net/total-energy/world-energy-intensity-gdp-data.html>
15. OECD. (2025). Sweden Energy and Resource Efficiency Trends. Retrieved from https://www.oecd.org/content/dam/oecd/en/publications/reports/2025/03/oecd-environmental-performance-reviews-sweden-2025_409c4061/91dcc109-en.pdf
16. Government of Canada. (2017). Clean Energy Factsheet. Retrieved from <https://www.canada.ca/content/dam/themes/environment/documents/weather1/20170119-en.pdf>
17. International Energy Agency (IEA). (n.d.). China's Renewable Energy Forecast. Retrieved from <https://www.iea.org/countries/china>
18. Eurostat. (n.d.). GDP Indicators. Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/nama_10_gdp/default/table?lang=en
19. Eurostat. (n.d.). Material Flow Accounts. Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/env_ac_mfa/default/table?lang=en
20. Eurostat. (n.d.). Resource Productivity. Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/env_ac_rp/default/table?lang=en
21. IEA. (n.d.). SDG 7: Energy Intensity Projections. Retrieved from <https://www.iea.org/reports/sdg7-data-and-projections/energy-intensity>
22. Eurostat. (n.d.). Resource Productivity Statistics Explained. Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Resource_productivity_statistics
23. World Bank. (n.d.). Renewable Energy Share (% of Total Final Energy Consumption). Retrieved from <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/EG.FEC.RNEW.ZS>
24. OECD. (2025). Sweden Environmental and Economic Integration Review. Retrieved from https://www.oecd.org/content/dam/oecd/en/publications/reports/2025/03/oecd-environmental-performance-reviews-sweden-2025_409c4061/91dcc109-en.pdf
25. IEA. (n.d.). China Renewable Expansion Overview. Retrieved from <https://www.iea.org/countries/china>
26. Judijanto, L. (2025, Februari). Green Economy and Resource Efficiency. Retrieved from <https://adisampublisher.org/index.php/nasional/article/download/1027/1069/2043>
27. Our World in Data. (n.d.). Domestic Material Consumption per Unit of GDP. Retrieved from <https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/domestic-material-consumption-per-unit-of-gdp>
28. IEA. (n.d.). Energy Statistics Data Browser. Retrieved from <https://www.iea.org/data-and-statistics/data-tools/energy-statistics-data-browser>

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

6-Maxsus son. Bakalavr talabalarining maqolalari to'plami

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin. Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>